

Oxidomolybdenum based catalysts for sulfoxidation reactions: A brief Review

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Molybdenum-catalyzed oxygen atom transfer reactions have attracted considerable interest due to their relevance to some biological processes. In this context, some oxidomolybdenum complexes are explored as catalysts for organic transformations such as oxidation reactions. The roles of oxidomolybdenum complexes as catalysts for sulfoxidation reactions under homogeneous and heterogeneous conditions are reviewed. The utilities of oxidomolybdenum complexes have been further extended for environmentally friendly oxidation of sulfides under aqueous conditions using hydrogen peroxide as green oxidant.

Keywords: Oxidomolybdenum, catalyst, sulfoxidation, green oxidant.

Introduction

Oxidation reactions are most fundamental transformations in organic synthesis^{1,2} e.g. oxidation of alcohols^{2a}, olefins^{2b}, thiols^{2c} and sulfides^{2d} to corresponding carbonyls, epoxides, disulfides and sulfoxides/sulfones, respectively. Among the above mentioned oxidized products, many sulfoxides and sulfones are used as versatile intermediates for synthesis of natural products³. Moreover, these compounds have been proved to be active pharmaceutical ingredients for several therapeutic drug molecules⁴. They often play important roles due to their anti-ulcer (proton pump inhibitor), antibacterial, antifungal, anti-atherosclerotic, anthelmintic, antihypertensive, and cardiotoxic activities.

Sulfoxidation of organic sulfides is a straightforward method for the selective preparation of sulfoxides or sulfones. Traditional approaches for sulfoxidation reactions involve the usage of peracids⁵ or halogen derivatives^{2d}; however, they yield stoichiometric amounts of environmentally undesired by-products. In recent days, alternative approaches involving the use of transition metal based catalysts along with eco-friendly hydrogen peroxide as oxidant have been developed for oxidation of sulfides⁶.

Molybdenum is earth abundant and belongs to a unique family of transition metals. Various oxido-forms of molybdenum are present in many enzymes viz. xanthine oxidase,

aldehyde oxidase and sulfite oxidase. Such enzymes accomplish important physiological redox functions in human body. Modeling of the molybdenum based enzymes mostly includes the study of oxygen atom transfer (OAT) reactions. Mechanistic aspects of oxidomolybdenum complexes catalyzed organic transformations, mostly oxidation reactions, are related to the understanding of functional activities of molybdenum based enzymes.

Use of oxidomolybdenum based catalysts for various organic transformations is a recent trend and reviewed by us and others⁷⁻¹¹. The purpose of the present review is to describe and update a variety of representative oxidomolybdenum based homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts for sulfoxidation reactions using peroxide based oxidants. Simple sulfoxidation protocols discussed in this review found practical use and hence highlighted at the last section.

1. Homogeneous catalysis

(a) Oxidomolybdenum cores with mono and/or bidentate ligands:

Oxidomolybdenum complexes having general formula $\text{Mo}(\text{O})_x(\text{O}_2)_y(\text{L})_z$ where **L** represent anionic/neutral ligands bearing one or more donor atoms are well known. However, utilization of such compounds as catalysts for sulfoxidation reactions has gained importance only in recent years (Fig. 1, Table 1).

Fig. 1. Oxidomolybdenum(VI) compounds, 1-6 and oxidodiperoxidomolybdenum(VI) compounds, 7-9 used for sulfoxidation reactions.

Table 1. Oxidation of sulfides using the catalysts 1-9

Sl. No.	Catalyst	Oxidant	Sulfide	Selectivity	Ref. No.
1.	1	TBHP	Thioanisole	Sulfone	12
2.	1	H ₂ O ₂	Aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	13
3.	2	H ₂ O ₂	Aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	14
4.	3	H ₂ O ₂	Aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	15
5.	4	TBHP	Thioanisole	Sulfoxide or sulfone	16
6.	5, 6	TBHP	Methyl- <i>p</i> -tolylsulfide	Sulfoxide	17
7.	7	TBHP	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides	18
8.	8	H ₂ O ₂	S in diesel	Sulfoxide or sulfone	20
9.	9	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides	21

Oxidation of thioanisole with *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide in benzene medium and in presence of MoO₂(acac)₂ (1) as catalyst produced methyl phenyl sulfone in 98% yield¹². Formation of peroxidomolybdenum species followed by electrophilic oxygen transfer to the sulfide is proposed in these reactions¹³. Catalytic amount of MoO₂Cl₂ (2) or its solvent adducts selectively catalyzed the oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides or sulfones by varying the amount of catalyst (1.5 or 15 mol%), oxidant i.e. H₂O₂ (1.05 or 4 equivalents) and solvent (acetone/water or acetonitrile)¹⁴. Importantly, the catalyst 2 could also selectively oxidize sulfides without harming sensitive substituents like olefin, acetylene, alcohol, aldehyde, ester and oxime when present in the sulfide. Whereas the use of 1 as a catalyst for sulfoxidation of an oxime

functionalized sulfide provided a mixture of compounds along with the targeted sulfoxide that included the starting sulfide, over-oxidized sulfone, cleavage of oxime bonds in the products and starting material etc.¹⁴.

Similarly, catalytic amount of MoO₃ (3) oxidized sulfides to sulfoxides and sulfones with 1.3 and 2.6 equivalents of 30% H₂O₂, respectively as an oxidant. Moreover MoO₃ (3) selectively oxidized the sulfides in the presence of alcohol and acetate functional groups¹⁵. The catalyst MoO₂(S-BINOL)(THF)₂ (4) successfully oxidized methyl phenyl sulfide to respective sulfoxide and sulfone in dichloromethane with 1 and 2 equivalents of 5–6 M TBHP in *n*-decane, respectively. Unfortunately, the catalyst showed less enantioselectivity¹⁶. The related complexes MoO₂Cl₂(L)₂

[where **L** = (*R*)-(+)-methyl-*p*-tolylsulfoxide, **5** or (*S,S*)-bis(*p*-tolyl sulfinyl)methane, **6**] were used as catalyst for the oxidation of methyl-*p*-tolylsulfide to corresponding sulfoxide in dry THF using 1.00 equivalent of 70% aq. TBHP as oxidant. The use of these catalysts could not give rise to any significant enantiomeric excess in the resulting sulfoxides¹⁷.

The molybdenum(VI) oxido-peroxido complex Mo(O)(O₂)(phox)₂, (**7**) has been found to be an excellent catalyst for oxidation of various aryl and aliphatic sulfides to sulfoxides in acetonitrile using TBHP as an oxidant¹⁸. A variety of Mo^{VI} complexes i.e. MoO₂X₂L₂ (X = halide or Me, **L** neutral ligand) behaved as catalysts for sulfoxidation reactions using H₂O₂ or TBHP as oxidant where the peroxide coordinated to molybdenum center transferred oxygen to the sulfides¹⁹. The oxidomolybdenum complex, MoO₂Cl₂(4,4'-di-*tert*-butyl-2,2'-bipyridine) as (pre)catalyst is utilized for oxidative desulfurization using 30% H₂O₂ as oxidant and an ionic liquid as extraction solvent. The (pre)catalyst was oxidized by H₂O₂ forming oxidodiperoxidomolybdenum(VI) complex (**8**) as an active catalyst for oxidative desulfurization reaction²⁰. Phase transfer bisguanidinium dinuclear oxidodiperoxidomolybdosulfate (**9**) efficiently acted as a catalyst and enantioselectively oxidized various sulfides with 35% H₂O₂ to corresponding sulfoxides with high *ee*²¹.

(b) Oxidomolybdenum core with tri or tetradentate ligands:

A variety of [MoO₂(L)(D)] type oxidomolybdenum complexes where **L** stands for tridentate ligand and "D" for additional monodentate ligand are known in literature²². The focus of this part of the review is to describe catalytic activities of such complexes and related complexes containing or ONOO type tetradentate ligand (**10-13**) for oxidation of sulfides (Fig. 2, Table 2).

The dioxidomolybdenum complex, [MoO₂(L)(CH₃OH)], **10** has been used for catalytic oxidation reaction of sulfides using urea hydrogen peroxide (UHP) as a green oxidant. The complex **10** oxidized various aliphatic and aryl sulfides to corresponding sulfoxides and sulfones using 1 and 5 equivalents of UHP, respectively²³. Similar kind of oxidomolybdenum complex **11** comprising of C₃ symmetric amino tris-*tert*-butyl phenolate ligand oxidized *p*-tolyl methyl sulfide to corresponding sulfoxide using 0.1 M aq. H₂O₂ as an oxidant²⁴. A series of *cis*-dioxidomolybdenum(VI) complexes with different chiral ONO-type ligands including **12** were synthesized and screened for oxidation reaction of aryl sulfides with 30% aq. H₂O₂ as an oxidant. The dioxidomolybdenum complex **12** shows good activity towards oxidation of sulfides to respective sulfoxide with moderate enantioselectivity²⁵. A series of related molybdenum(VI) complexes containing 4,6-O-ethylidene-β-D-glucopyranosylamine derived ligands (e.g. **13**) have been employed for selective oxidation of sulfides

Fig. 2. Oxidomolybdenum(VI) compounds **10-13** used for sulfoxidation reactions.

Table 2. Oxidation of sulfides using the catalysts **10-13**

Sl. No.	Catalyst	Oxidant	Sulfide	Selectivity	Ref. No.
1.	10	UHP	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	23
2.	11	H ₂ O ₂	<i>p</i> -Tolyl methyl sulfide	Sulfoxide	24
3.	12	H ₂ O ₂	Aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides	25
4.	13	H ₂ O ₂	Aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides	26

Table 3. Oxidation of sulfides using the catalysts **14-19**

Sl. No.	Catalyst	Oxidant	Sulfide	Selectivity	Ref. No.
1.	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O, 14	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfones	28
2.	[(<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉) ₄ N] ₄ (α-Mo ₈ O ₂₆), 15	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides	29
3.	Na ₃ [CrMo ₆ O ₂₄ H ₆]·8H ₂ O, 16	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfones	30
4.	(PyH)(H ₃ PMo ₁₁ VO ₄₀), 17	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	31
5.	Mo ₇₂ Cr ₃₀ , 18	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfones	32
6.	[Bmim] ₄ Mo ₈ O ₂₆ , 19	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	33

to the corresponding sulfoxides using 1 equivalent UHP as an oxidant. All molybdenum complexes related to **13** showed good activities towards sulfides and corresponding sulfoxides are obtained in good to excellent yields²⁶.

(c) *Polyoxidomolybdate cores:*

Polyoxidometalates including polyoxido molybdates are known for a variety of organic transformations²⁷. The major focus of this part of review is oxidation of various sulfides using polyoxidomolybdate as catalyst and peroxide as oxidant (Table 3). A simple and efficient method for the oxidation of sulfides to sulfones at room temperature is developed using ammonium heptamolybdate, (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O (**14**) as catalyst with 4 equivalents of 30% H₂O₂ as an oxidant. The reactions provided excellent yields of sulfones and sensitive functional groups such as allyl, vinyl, propargyl, alcohol, ketone, ester, pyridine and nitrile were found to be tolerated²⁸. Tetra-(tetraalkylammonium)octamolybdate, [(*n*-C₄H₉)₄N]₄(α-Mo₈O₂₆) (**15**) was successfully demonstrated for selective oxidation of various sulfides to sulfoxides with 30% aqueous hydrogen peroxide as oxidant under mild reaction conditions. The catalyst **15** tolerated active functional groups like hydroxyl and C=C bond while doing oxidation of sulfides under optimized condition²⁹. The selective oxidation of sulfides to corresponding sulfones are achieved by an Anderson-type catalyst sodium hexamolybdochromate(III) (**16**) with 30% H₂O₂ in acetonitrile at 60°C. The catalyst **16** successfully oxidized several diaryl, alkyl-aryl and dialkyl sulfides to respective sulfones with high yields³⁰. Heteropolycompounds were screened for controlled oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides and sulfones using 35% H₂O₂ as an oxidant. An acidic salt of heteropolycompound, (PyH)(H₃PMo₁₁VO₄₀), **17** was found to be an effective cata-

lyst for oxidation of various aliphatic and aryl sulfides with oxidant (35% H₂O₂) to sulfoxides and sulfones in acetonitrile at 20°C and 40°C, respectively³¹. The catalytic activity of three polyoxidometalates, Mo₇₂M₃₀ (M = V, Cr, Fe) are screened for oxidation of various sulfides to sulfones in water using 30% H₂O₂ as an oxidant. Among three catalysts, Mo₇₂Cr₃₀ (**18**) showed high catalytic activities towards environmentally friendly oxidation of various allyl and aryl sulfides with aqueous 30% H₂O₂³². The four alkyl imidazolium and pyridinium salts based octamolybdates were screened for controlled oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides and sulfones with 1.5 and 3 equivalence 30% H₂O₂, respectively. Among the four octamolybdates, [Bmim]₄Mo₈O₂₆ (Bmim = 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium), **19** showed good catalytic activity towards oxidation of sulfides in acetonitrile. Moreover the catalyst **19** showed excellent reusability upto 8 cycles³³. A chiral bisguanidinium dinuclear complex oxidodiperoxidomolybdosulfate [(μ-SO₄)Mo₂O₂(μ-O₂)₂(O₂)₂]²⁻ (**9**) is an ion pair and acted as a catalyst for enantioselective sulfoxidation using aqueous H₂O₂ as terminal oxidant^{21,34}.

2. Heterogeneous catalysis

A number of heterogeneous molybdenum based catalysts have been exploited for different kind of oxidation reactions³⁵. In this part of review, oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides and/or sulfones is discussed (Fig. 3, Table 4).

The polymeric catalyst [MoO₃(2,2'-bipy)]_n (**20**) is employed for the oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides and sulfones, using *tert*-butylhydroperoxide as the stoichiometric oxidant. The catalyst possesses several advantages because of its stability and possibilities of recycling³⁶. Enantioselective oxidation of thioanisole in water was explored by Mo^{VI} supramo-

Fig. 3. Molybdenum complexes **20-28** used for sulfoxidation reactions.Table 4. Oxidation of sulfides using the catalysts **20-28**

Sl. No.	Catalyst	Oxidant	Sulfide	Selectivity	Ref. No.
1.	[MoO ₃ (2,2'-bipy)] _n , 20	TBHP	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	36
2.	β-CD-Mo ^{VI} , 21	H ₂ O ₂	Thioanisole	Sulfoxide	37
3.	Mo-Si sample, 22	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides	38
4.	Silica coated-MoO(O ₂) ₂ (OPyr), 23	–	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	39
5.	β-CD-Mo ^V , 24	H ₂ O ₂	Aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides	40
6.	Supported-PMo ₁₂ O ₄₀ , 25	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfones	41
7.	Supported-MoO ₂ Cl ₂ , 26	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides	42
8.	Supported-[Mo(O) ₂ (O ₂)(L) ₂] ²⁻ , 27a/b	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	43
9.	(CTA) ₂ [MoO(O ₂) ₂ (C ₂ O ₄)]·H ₂ O, 28	H ₂ O ₂	Aliphatic and aryl sulfides	Sulfoxides or sulfones	45

lecular catalysts with β-cyclodextrin-based ligands using 30% H₂O₂ as an oxidant. The Mo^{VI} complex, **21** showed moderate enantioselectivity towards oxidation of thioanisole to methyl phenyl sulfoxide³⁷. Selective catalytic oxidation of thioethers to sulfoxides by using a special type of Mo-silicate sample on an organic template with Si/Mo ratio of 80,

22 and 30% H₂O₂ as an oxidant was explored. The catalyst **22** oxidized various types of alkyl and aryl sulfides to corresponding sulfoxides³⁸. Oxidodiperoxidomolybdenum complex [MoO(O₂)₂(OPyr)(H₂O)] was coated with silica gel to prepare the material, **23** that was explored for the oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides selectively³⁹. Equimolar amount of

corresponding uncoated Mo^{VI} complex however oxidized aliphatic and aryl sulfides to sulfones³⁹. The modified β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) derivatives having catechol-type ligand (2,3- and 3,4-dihydroxy groups on the benzoate ring) are synthesized and corresponding Mo^V complexes are used for enantioselective oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides. The molybdenum complex **24** oxidized different aryl sulfides to sulfoxides in good yields with moderate enantioselectivity⁴⁰. The molybdenum based heteropolyacid (H₃PMo₁₂O₄₀), immobilized on aminopropyl-functionalized silica catalyst, **25** could catalyze the oxidation of aliphatic and aromatic sulfides to corresponding sulfoxides. The catalyst shows good catalytic activity towards various sulfides with 35% H₂O₂ as an oxidant and corresponding sulfones are isolated in good yields⁴¹.

The oxidomolybdenum complex MoO₂Cl₂(DMF)₂ immobilized on different polystyrene resins as ligands and resulting Mo^{VI} complexes are used for oxidation of sulfides. The catalyst **26** shows good catalytic activity towards various aliphatic and aryl sulfides to sulfoxides with good yields⁴². The heterogeneous catalysts supported-[MoO₂(O₂)(L)₂]²⁻, **27a/b** [where, L = valine or alanine] immobilized on Merrifield resin, which exhibit excellent activity, stability and selectivity for the oxidation of sulfides to the corresponding sulfoxides and sulfones with H₂O₂ at ambient temperature⁴³. Catalysis using metallomicellar compounds under aqueous conditions is considered versatile and ecofriendly for organic transformations⁴⁴. A new molybdenum based metallomicellar catalyst (C₁₉H₄₂N)₂[MoO(O₂)₂(C₂O₄)·H₂O], **28** was developed and utilized for oxidation of various sulfides to sulfoxides and sulfones using 1 and 3 equivalents of 30% H₂O₂, respectively as oxidant. The micro heterogeneous metallomicellar catalyst **28** depicted good recyclability in water⁴⁵.

3. Practical applications

Literature search on the actual use of molybdenum complexes considered in this review revealed noteworthy points. The catalyst **1** (MoO₂(acac)₂) is known for deprotection of acetals⁴⁶ and found to be useful in organic synthesis⁴⁷. So far as sulfoxidation reactions are concerned, the catalyst **2** (MoO₂Cl₂) behaved profoundly. Selective and controlled oxidation of sulfides to corresponding sulfoxides or sulfones using a mild catalyst system MoO₂Cl₂, **2** is presented in Table

1, entry 3. This catalyst also tolerated a variety of sensitive functional groups present in the substrate and hence attracted wide attention. The protocols found practical uses in different laboratories for synthesis of targeted sulfoxides/sulfones⁴⁸.

Conclusion

In recent years, oxidomolybdenum based catalysts are being established for various oxidation reactions. A notable progress has been made especially for oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides and sulfones. Sulfide oxidation using peroxide (ROOH) as terminal oxidant and carried out in organic media is usually practiced. A definite outlook in this field would be to develop workable oxidomolybdenum complexes as catalyst that could be utilized under aqueous conditions. This would allow fine chemical production of sulfoxides and sulfones in industrial scale while taking care of the environment.

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